

European funds and green public procurement

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Summary

1. To stimulate sustainable economic development and a greener economy, the European Commission co-funds public projects through the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF). Beneficiaries receiving funding from ESIF are explicitly incentivized to increase their use of green public procurement (GPP) since 2014.
2. The availability of funding from ESIF has a small but significant and positive effect on the uptake of GPP in Czechia.
3. The effect on GPP is driven by financial incentives and not by ‘greener’ policy objectives.
4. It appears that ESIF co-funding instigates selection behaviour by contracting authorities, that allocate their projects and resources to improve their chances of receiving co-funding.
5. Gained experience with GPP increases contracting authorities’ later uptake of GPP to a very limited extent.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) has initiated a comprehensive set of actions through the European Green Deal, aiming to shift towards a clean, climate-neutral, and circular economy by the year 2050 (EC, 2019). As public procurement represents about 14% of the EU's GDP (EC, 2023) and significantly contributes to global greenhouse gas emissions (WEF & BCG, 2022), the EU recognizes public procurement as a key tool for promoting sustainable industry practices

and, in general, to achieve the goals of the Green Deal (EC, 2019, 2020).

Since 2014, ESIF explicitly promotes the uptake of GPP and requires beneficiaries to ensure the full mainstreaming of sustainability into public procurement (EC, 2015, p. 145). In this policy brief, we discuss whether and to what extent ESIF causes higher adoption of GPP.

ESIF mainly focuses on EU Member States and regions with lower economic development, providing joint funding for public projects to encourage sustainable development at the regional level. We present

key findings from the underlying academic research conducted by Nicolas, et al. (2023), that exploits an extensive database that exploits an extensive database of public procurement contracts from Czechia covering the period 2006-2019 and study the effects of the availability of co-funding from ESIF on the uptake of GPP. Although this policy brief discusses findings that directly apply to the Czech Republic only, it is likely that the situation is similar in other Member States in the region of Central and Eastern Europe. Czechia is quite representative of the region in terms of economic development and government capacity.

2. Main Findings

There are three critical policy questions that we aim to answer in this policy brief. Firstly, there is a relatively small but significant and positive effect of ESIF co-funding on GPP in public tenders. An increase of 2.8 percentage points in GPP uptake is caused by the availability of ESIF co-funding. This is a relatively limited impact given the amount of resources spent through ESIF and the fact that about 30% of public procurement contracts in Czechia are co-funded. One of the reasons behind that is that it appears that authorities may be selectively allocating projects for co-funding that are more likely to incorporate green procurement practices. This selection behaviour reflects strategic decision-making by authorities to maximize the chances of receiving ESIF co-funding. If each contract being co-funded was also sustainable and there were no selection and spillover effects, the effect of ESIF co-funding of the same size as now would be a 30 percentage points increase and not 2.8 percentage points. This shows that the policy conditions do not translate to practice.

Secondly, the underlying academic study examines what drives the stimulating effect of ESIF on GPP uptake. Contrary to what might be expected, the findings suggest that the temporary surge in GPP is financially driven and not by a shift towards 'greener' ESIF policy objectives. While the actual uptake of GPP changes significantly in periods where more co-funding is available, it remains on par in periods when the policy changed to explicitly target sustainability objectives. This conclusion can be drawn from the comparison of different funding periods over the studied period and it implies that the primary motivator for GPP adoption in Czechia is the availability of financial resources.

Thirdly, the underlying research shows that while contracting authorities with GPP experience in the previous year are slightly more likely to employ it in current tenders, this effect is marginal and consistent across projects with or without ESIF co-funding. This outcome suggests that, while experience with GPP is beneficial, it does not significantly improve the likelihood of its future adoption to an extent that would sustain GPP uptake levels in the absence of financial support.

3. Discussion and Policy Recommendations

The implications of these findings are relevant for policy. The current design of the ESIF co-funding mechanism achieves changes in the uptake of GPP of limited economic significance. The project-based type of funding appears unsuitable to achieve the intended mainstreaming of sustainability (although it can be suitable to achieve goals such as economic growth et cetera). The tendency of contracting authorities to focus their sustainable behaviour on projects that are more likely to secure co-funding suggests

that a more refined policy design is needed. The current outcome of the policy is that projects already planned as sustainable are co-funded, rather than a large shift towards more sustainable projects, in proportion to the funds.

Previous experience with green procurement projects has a small effect on green procurement behaviour. This means that ESIF co-funding sustainable public projects is not likely to have lasting effects on procurement and that the increase in green procurement is likely to wane in a country such as Czechia once the funding dries up.

We argue for a re-evaluation of funding strategies, aiming for more enduring and impactful outcomes in sustainable procurement across Europe. It appears important to heed of selection behaviour and to introduce conditions that motivate green behaviour at the national level or at the level of the contracting authority rather than a project or contract level.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

Nicolas, R., Titl, V. & F. Schotanus (2023). European funds and green public procurement. USE Working Paper Series 23-10. URL: https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/LEG_USE_WP_23-10.pdf

DemoTrans is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101059288). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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